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Language quality, content, structure: What analytic ratings tell us about EFL writing skills at upper secondary school level in Germany and Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Argumentative writing in English as a foreign language (EFL) is an important skill in upper secondary education in Germany and Switzerland. This article provides insights into students' EFL writing skills in the aspects of *language quality*, *content*, and *structure* (N = 2314 TOEFL argumentative essays from two time-points, beginning and end of Year 11). These essays were analyzed by trained human raters using analytic assessment rubrics for each aspect and evaluated in a cross-sectional as well as a longitudinal perspective. Results show that there were significant variations between these aspects in learners' texts, suggesting that they represent separate dimensions of the argumentative writing ability. Scores were lowest for language quality, suggesting that this was the most challenging aspect for EFL learners. Learning gains over one year were largest for structure, smaller for content and smallest for language quality. Overall, learners in Switzerland showed higher skills in all three aspects, but German learners showed larger gains in structure over the school year. Implications for classroom learning and further research are discussed.

1. Introduction

The importance of writing for educational success has long been recognized in the European context (Keller, Fleckenstein, Krüger, Köller & Rupp, 2020; Köller et al., 2010; Landrieu, De Smedt, Van Keer & De Wever, 2022; Schoonen, 2005). Writing in English as a foreign language (EFL) is an important competence for succeeding in many academic disciplines, serves to promote language awareness, and is a means of supporting foreign language acquisition in general (Akukwe et al., 2017). Further, EFL writing is key for success in tertiary education and employment in an increasingly globalized world (Keller, 2013). Writing in general benefits learning in a range of subjects such as social studies, sciences, and mathematics (Graham et al., 2020). Additionally, EFL writing is often used as a proxy for language ability in both standardized tests and language acquisition studies, leading to a greater interest in examining

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textual features (Crossley, 2020).

English EFL curricula at upper secondary level (ISCED 3) in Germany and Switzerland stipulate that learners should be able to organize their ideas, structure their writing, and use appropriate language and tone in expressing themselves on a range of culturally relevant topics in English (Swiss Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education [EDK], 1994; Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs of the Länder in the Federal Republic of Germany [KMK], 2014). To check whether learners have mastered these objectives, previous studies have used holistic ratings to measure the writing ability of EFL learners in these two countries (Keller et al., 2020). Internationally, studies have focused mainly on language-related aspects (i.e., lexical or syntactical features) when discussing EFL writing development (Barkaoui & Hadidi, 2020; Crossley, 2020; Kim, 2021; Kyle et al., 2021). Yet, as Polio (2017) points out, “writing development concerns much more than lexical-grammatical development” (p. 266). EFL writing is a many-faceted and complex construct, its study requiring the analysis of varied aspects of communication such as gauging readers’ responses, choosing correct levels of register and style (Cumming, 2012), argumentation strategies (Hyland, 1990). Ideally, all these aspects should be considered when describing the development of learners’ L2 writing skills in a specific genre or educational setting (Tardy, 2006; Tardy & Swales, 2014).

This paper hopes to make an impact by presenting a repeated measurement study on three broad aspects of learners’ argumentative EFL writing skills: (1) language quality defined as learners’ command of genre-specific lexical items, grammatical structures, and ability to use argumentative language; (2) content defined as the ability to construct a stringent argument in response to the writing prompt that includes arguments for both sides of the question and appropriate support; and (3) structure defined as the ability to divide an essay into an introduction, main part, and conclusion, and to use paragraphing effectively to support argumentation. It presents both a cross-sectional analysis by comparing results from different countries (Switzerland and Germany), and a longitudinal one by comparing results over a period of (roughly) one school year.

We have structured this paper into four parts, as follows: in the Background section, we summarize relevant research on the educational context of EFL learning in Switzerland and Germany. In the Methods section, we describe the development of the analytic rating system, rater training, and statistical analyses conducted in this study. We subsequently describe developmental trajectories of learners’ EFL writing skills for language quality, content, and structure in the Results section, also focusing on differences between the two educational systems. Finally, we discuss the relevance for teaching argumentative EFL writing together with limitations and perspectives for further research.

2. Background

2.1. Key aspects of EFL argumentative essays

Learning to write in a foreign language means mastering the conventions of specific genres, including the ability to use language in conventionalized social settings and in accordance with a set of communicative goals (Bhatia, 2004; Hyland, 2008). Genres channel communicative interactions but also exclude language users who are unfamiliar with their normalized practices (Tardy & Swales, 2014). In the genre of argumentative writing, learners must be able to use appropriate grammatical structures and lexical items (including argumentative language) to construct arguments over several paragraphs and to structure these paragraphs in a way that conforms to genre-expectations (Ferretti & Lewis, 2019).

Due to their central position in many educational contexts, English argumentative essays are a well-described genre in terms of their internal structure and textual moves (Hyland, 1990). In Table 1, we have summarized central elements of argumentative essays which are mentioned in linguistic and educational studies both in the L1 and L2 contexts. Taken together, they constitute a set of learning goals at the level of language quality, content and structure which students must master to write successfully in this genre.

The elements listed in Table 1 are typically also mentioned in relevant analytic scoring rubrics. As Cushing (2019) notes, most of these rubrics tend to have at least one subscale for content (or ideas), one for organization, and one for language-related aspects (grammar, vocabulary, mechanics.). In high-quality argumentative essays, these elements are combined to support the writer’s

Table 1

Central Elements of English Argumentative Essays (Ferretti & Lewis, 2019; Hyland, 1990; Staples et al., 2018; Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008).

	Correctness / appropriateness of vocabulary
	Correctness / appropriateness of grammar
	Control of language mechanics
	Style and register
Language quality	Argumentative language (e. g., structuring words and cohesive devices such as however, first, second, finally, etc.)
	Appropriate and relevant content
Content	Constructing a stringent argument (pros / cons)
	Finding and listing adequate support
	Well-defined introduction
	Main part with body paragraphs
	Well-defined conclusion
Structure	Paragraphing supporting understanding argumentation

argument, refute counter arguments and convince readers of the writer's point of view (Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008).

As an indication of how well foreign language learners at upper secondary level cope with these challenges, a recent study of 130 argumentative EFL essays in the Netherlands is instructive (Landrieu et al., 2022). It found systematic differences in argumentation between weak, mid-range and strong essays. Weak texts were characterized by a lack of claim or arguments, poor factual accuracy, and poor writing mechanics. Strong texts, by contrast, showed high quality of argumentation (claims, arguments, rebuttals), high quality of content (strong persuasiveness and factual accuracy) and text structure (introduction, conclusion), as well as a high level of linguistic correctness.

2.2. Studies of L2 writers' longitudinal development

While there is much cross-sectional research on EFL writing skills (e.g., Landrieu et al., 2022), fewer studies have examined learners' longitudinal L2 writing development (Barkaoui & Hadidi, 2020; Cumming, 2012; Cushing, 2019; Kyle et al. 2021; Polio, 2017). Further, most longitudinal studies have focused on how development in the linguistic characteristics of learners' L2 texts is reflected in changes in their writing scores (Barkaoui & Hadidi, 2020). As Polio (2017) has argued, more longitudinal research should be conducted on specific genres and tasks of L2 writing while also including a wider range of aspects of text quality. This would involve both observational and implementation studies to understand how writing skills develop over time.

An important theory of learners' longitudinal foreign language development is usage-based theory, which posits that learning occurs as a function of language use: language items that are heard and used more frequently are more salient for learners, meaning that they will be learned earlier or more easily than those that are encountered less frequently (Kyle et al., 2021; Verspoor, 2017). Most studies in this paradigm have focused on lexical and syntactical complexity or sophistication to track the development of their L2 writing proficiency (e.g., Kim, 2021). For lexical features, studies have shown that L2 learners tend to use a higher proportion of low-frequency words as they become more proficient, while also being more likely to use those words in more target-like multiword constructions (Crossley, 2020; Kyle et al., 2021). In terms of phrasal sophistication, features in L2 writing do not generally become more sophisticated, but rather develop toward being more acceptable. This means that advanced L2 writers more strongly follow the phrasal patterns which L1 writers would use in similar situations (Crossley, 2020). In terms of syntactical development, proficient L2 writers tend to produce longer and more varied syntactic structures than less proficient ones (Lu, 2011), and also tend to use greater clausal subordination (Crossley, 2020; Kyle et al., 2021).

While development in such lexical and syntactical aspects of writing skills is well documented, the picture is sketchier for the aspect of content. As Crossley (2020) points out, content in argumentative writing is intensely connected with argumentative aspects of claims, theses, and rhetorical moves. While all these aspects are important for (L2) writing, they are seldom studied because they are not linguistic in nature (although based on language features). In a study in primary level EFL writing, Bae et al. (2016) showed that content significantly correlated with the linguistic features grammar (.35) and vocabulary (.37), as well as coherence, originality and text length. The study went as far as claiming that content "can be defined as the sum of these five elements" (p. 302). In a study on the association of skill-learning and L2 writing development, Francis et al. (2002) also showed a clear connection between content-related and language-related aspects. In sample of American EFL learners' writing in science education, learners who expressed more complex ideas also used more complex sentence structures. Content-related variables were highly correlated with language-related ones (esp. sentence complexity), suggesting that the complexity of learners' ideas increased in lockstep with their capacity to express those ideas. Such studies show how formal L2 skills are linked with content-related dimensions, underscoring the value of integrating these aspects in studies of EFL writing development.

Maybe the least well understood area of EFL writing (in terms of longitudinal development) is structure. In a study that focused on EFL learners in lower secondary education in Germany, Siekmann et al. (2022) showed that creating convincing structure and argumentative coherence was particularly difficult for learners in Year 9, and that essential parts of argumentative essays such as the conclusion were often missing. In general, EFL learners struggled to establish a broad common thread in their argumentation, with argumentative structure being a strong distinguishing feature between more and less proficient texts.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on the development of structure in upper-secondary EFL writing in Germany or Switzerland, and only few internationally. One could assume that this aspect is linked with the development of the learners' linguistic writing ability as they gain more lexical and grammatical ways of making the relationship between different textual elements explicit (Francis et al., 2002). Further, structuring an essay into introduction, main part and conclusion is a typical feature of school-related argumentative writing which learners also experience in their L1 (for Germany, see Bremerich-Vos & Scholten-Akoun, 2016), and which might be transferable to some degree between languages (Schnoor & Ursanova, 2022). These assumptions have never been tested, however, for the context in which this study took place.

Overall, one can say that of the complex construct that is L2 writing development, linguistic features of text quality are well researched while the picture is sketchier for content and structure. Our study aims to fill this research gap by including all three elements in its analysis, combining a cross-sectional with longitudinal approach.

2.3. Expected size of development

For a study that looks at the effectiveness of educational systems in fostering L2 writing skills, the question of expected learning gains is especially relevant. The study by Keller et al. (2020) showed that learning rates for EFL writing in Year 11 in Switzerland and Germany corresponded to effect sizes of about $d = 0.2$. While Swiss students did better overall, there were no differential growth effects between countries, and the effectiveness of both educational systems in teaching learners argumentative writing skills was similar ($d = 0.19$ for Germany and 0.18 for Switzerland). Such gains were in line with the annual gains in effect size for nationally normed reading tests for school Years 11–12 reported in a meta-analysis by Bloom, Hill, Black, and Lipsey (2008). Further, a recent study from Germany by Brunner et al. (2023) showed that the mean increase in proficiency in English at lower secondary level (Years 8 and 9) was $d = 0.27$. No data for English at upper secondary level were given in that study, but across different subjects, the annual academic growth in Years 11–12 was $d = 0.18$. Such effect sizes are a useful means of comparison for this study.

2.4. Holistic and analytic text analysis

The quality of any empirical study of writing hinges on the appropriateness of scoring rubrics and assessment procedures (Cushing, 2019). In the measurement literature, these procedures are typically divided into holistic and analytic assessment, with corresponding rubrics (Bacha, 2001; Barkaoui, 2010; Cushing, 2019; Grotjahn & Kleppin, 2017; Huot, 1990). In holistic assessment, raters assess a text as a whole and focus on its overall meaning and message. This type of rating is often used in timed-writing and large-scale contexts and tends to result in higher inter-rater agreement (Barkaoui, 2007; Rupp, Casabianca, Krüger, Keller & Köller, 2019; Staples et al., 2018). In analytic assessment, by contrast, raters base their valuation of individual text features on separate scales, aiming at identifying specific patterns and characteristics of a text (Schipolowski & Böhme, 2016). This type of scoring provides insights into individual aspects of writing and is a basis for detailed formative assessment and feedback in the classroom (Andrade, 2005).

In a previous study of upper secondary learners' EFL argumentative writing skills in Switzerland and Germany, Keller et al. (2020) showed that at the end of Year 11, about 75 % of students reached level B2 or higher according to the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages* (CEFR; Council of Europe, 2001). It further showed that about 25 % of students were still at level B1 at the second measurement point, and thus at risk of failing to acquire basic EFL argumentative skills for higher education. However, the study did not provide any insights into individual subskills of writing due to its holistic scoring method.

The current study used analytic scoring to focus on three broad aspects of the EFL writing ability (language quality, structure and content) and sought to track them in a longitudinal design. This type of analysis can account for the fact that developing learners typically perform at different proficiency levels in different sub-skills (Bacha, 2001; Kroll, 1990). For example, an analytic analysis of German first graders' L1 essays (Pohlmann-Rother et al., 2016) showed a two-dimensional structure of writing skills, with semantic-pragmatic aspects of writing distinct from language-systematic aspects. Trüb (2022) showed that Swiss EFL learners' texts in Year 6 contained considerable inter-individual heterogeneity regarding different dimensions of text quality. While individual texts might be internally heterogeneous in quality, studies also show that different traits of EFL writing are systematically correlated even if they concern quite distinct aspects of text quality. Bae & Bachman (2010), for example, showed that grammar, content, spelling, and text length were all significantly correlated in English and Korean elementary school learners' writing. This was true both for related aspects (spelling and grammar, .89) and relatively unrelated ones (spelling and text length, .53). In the same vein, this study operationalizes theoretically motivated aspects of writing quality which can be assumed to be related to some degree, yet which are considered conceptually different for gaining a differentiated picture of learners' writing development and for supporting that development in the classroom.

2.5. EFL writing in Switzerland and Germany

EFL writing curricula in Germany and Switzerland are both based on the CEFR (Council of Europe, 2001) in terms of the level which learners are expected to attain at the end of upper secondary education, namely level B2 (Fleckenstein, Keller, Krüger, Tannenbaum & Köller, 2019). Argumentative writing at this level involves students being able to present clear, detailed descriptions on a wide range of subjects, to explain their viewpoint on topical issues, and to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of various options relating to a specific prompt (Council of Europe, 2001). For students surpassing these basic requirements, EFL argumentative writing further includes the development of specific arguments in an introduction, the integration of sub-themes of argumentation, and the appropriate closing of a text with a conclusion (Council of Europe, 2001).

Upper-secondary level English curricula in both countries specify that learners should be able to address different argumentative positions, use a repertoire of syntactic structures and lexical expressions to express their opinion, and show command of English language mechanics (Fleckenstein et al., 2019). These are also the requirements for passing the TOEFL writing exams, which often serve as college entrance exams in international contexts (Educational Testing Service [ETS], 2009).

While the curricula for EFL writing in the two countries are similar, the two countries differ in terms of selectiveness of these educational tracks. In Switzerland, about 21 % of learners attend higher secondary education (Gymnasium), compared to 35 % in Germany (National Statistical Office of Switzerland [BFS], 2016). A previous study on differences in EFL learners' argumentative

writing skills between these countries (Keller et al., 2020) showed that learners in Switzerland outperformed students in Germany both at the beginning and at the end of 11th year, i.e., the penultimate year of upper-secondary education. On the holistic TOEFL iBT writing assessment scale (Educational Testing Service [ETS], 2009), Swiss students were ahead of German ones by about a third of a standard deviation, which translates into an advantage of 15–16 months in terms of schooling time (Keller et al., 2020). Both national samples showed similar proficiency gains over one school year so that the difference in achievement levels remained largely unchanged at the end of Year 11. As no significant influences of gender, social background or linguistic background on writing development were detected in either country, authors attributed this difference to the structure of the national educational systems. For example, the sample from Switzerland contained a higher percentile of high-performing learners at the second time-point (18.4 % at CEFR levels C1/C2) than the sample from Germany (11.4 % at levels C1/C2), where access to upper-level schooling is less selective and heterogeneity of proficiency levels is larger (Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education in Germany [KMK], 2018; Keller et al., 2020).

A further difference between the two countries is the way argumentative EFL writing is tested at the end of upper secondary education. In Switzerland, there are no mandatory standards of assessment at the end of secondary education (Keller, 2013). While EFL argumentative writing figures prominently in the curricula, it is left to the responsibility of individual districts (often, individual schools) to what extent they want to test argumentative writing in the final exams (Swiss Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education EDK, 1994).

Germany, by contrast, has national educational standards for upper secondary education designating argumentative writing as a core element of upper secondary EFL education. These standards are tested in a pool of mandatory assessment tasks at final exams (Institute for Educational Quality Improvement [IQB], 2021). These assessment tasks include a section on reading and understanding argumentative texts, a section on interpreting argumentative structures and rhetorical devices, and a section on writing an argumentative essay, either in response to the input texts or as a personal statement. Further, national assessment criteria exist for these tasks, comprising the aspects language quality and content. To achieve high marks in content (which also contains aspects of structure), students are expected to write texts which are highly structured, free from redundancy, and coherent in argumentation. In language quality, particular emphasis is given to lexis and grammar as well as consistent functional use of text-structuring means (cohesion) (IQB, 2021).

As this study focused on aspects of EFL writing explicitly mentioned in the relevant curricula, it allowed us to test whether there is a backwash effect of these standards on teaching, possibly leading to a differential development of writing skills in the two countries which had not been discernible in the earlier, holistic analysis.

We formulated two main research questions for this study:

- (1) How does the quality of learners' argumentative essays develop over one year regarding language quality, structure and content?
- (2) Are there any differences in writing skills and learning gains over one school year in argumentative EFL writing in Switzerland and Germany in terms of language quality, content and structure?

The first research question concerns the longitudinal development of writing skills over one school year, the second additionally focuses on the influence of different educational systems and student populations.

3. Method

3.1. Sample and procedure

Data collection was carried out as a repeated measurement design in upper secondary schools in Germany and Switzerland with an interval of nine months between the two measurement points (T1: August/September 2016; T2: May/June 2017). In Switzerland, schools from seven German-speaking cantons (districts) were asked whether they wanted to participate in the study. Data were collected from 91 classes nested in 20 schools, resulting in a sample size of $N = 1882$ Swiss students (58 % female; age $M_{T1} = 17.56$, $SD_{T1} = 0.91$; $M_{T2} = 18.27$, $SD_{T2} = 0.91$). In Germany, data were gathered in the federal state of Schleswig-Holstein, where 42 schools were randomly selected from the pool of 84 available schools and students were asked for their voluntary participation. In the end, $N = 965$ students from different upper secondary profiles (e.g., language, science, civics) were included in the study (58.6 % female; age $M_{T1} = 16.91$, $SD_{T1} = 0.56$; $M_{T2} = 17.61$, $SD_{T2} = 0.56$).

Data collection took place on laptops provided by the research team in a rotational matrix design where the order in which learners worked on the two argumentative writing prompts at T1 and T2 was randomly varied to minimize sequence effects (Rupp et al., 2019).

3.2. Writing prompts

To operationalize EFL argumentative writing skills, the study used prompts from the TOEFL iBT® writing section (Educational Testing Service [ETS], 2009). They were chosen because the TOEFL assessment rubric aligns well with the relevant writing curricula in Germany and Switzerland (Educational Testing Service [ETS], 2009; Fleckenstein et al., 2020). In general, TOEFL-iBT® language tests

(and particularly the writing section) have been shown to be responsive to longitudinal development in similar studies involving L2 learners (Barkaoui & Hadidi, 2020; Choi & Papageorgiou, 2014; Ling et al., 2024). Further, learner texts on these prompts can be reliably linked to the competence levels of the CEFR (Fleckenstein et al., 2020).

The following two prompts were chosen: “A teacher’s ability to relate well with students is more important than excellent knowledge of the subject being taught” (*Teacher*, or TE prompt); and “Television advertising directed toward young children (aged two to five) should not be allowed” (*Advertising*, or AD prompt). Participants were asked to provide detailed reasons for their arguments in a text of approximately 300 words. The writing time was 30 min, and there was no preparation or support (i.e., dictionaries, etc.). In a pilot study, the research team tested the suitability of these prompts in classes of identical school level and type, checking whether they were within the ability range of the target student populations (Rupp et al., 2019). As neither floor nor ceiling effects were observed, these prompts were then re-used in the main study.

3.3. Analytic assessment of learner texts

The original dataset from Keller et al. (2020) contains $N = 5694$ texts for the AD and TE prompts (i.e. independent writing TOEFL-iBT®) from two time points. Due to the high intensity and cost of rater training and operational scoring, it was beyond the reach of this study to include the whole dataset in the extended analysis. For this reason, we randomly selected $N = 2314$ texts from the original dataset for re-analysis, equally balancing texts on the TE and the AD prompt at both time points.

The analytic categories of language quality, structure and content were selected for three reasons. First, we wanted to generate features which represented aspects of the writing ability that could be linked coherently to educational curricula in participating countries (Fleckenstein et al., 2020). Second, we wanted to measure aspects that were congruent with categories of analysis described in the pedagogical literature on EFL argumentative writing in school contexts (e.g., Cushing, 2019; Jacobs, Zinkgraf, Wormuth, Hearfiel & Hughey, 1981). And third, we wanted to generate sufficient statistical reliability by basing each aspect on a set of clearly defined items (sub-scales) which were simple and unambiguous enough for raters to handle in operational scoring (see also 3.5. below).

For this purpose, the research team designed a rating scheme based on existing descriptions and assessment rubrics of EFL argumentative writing (Ferretti & Lewis, 2019; Hyland, 1990; Jacobs et al., 1981; Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008). Individual sub-scales were developed in co-operation with experts from the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) Data Processing and Research Center (DPC) in Hamburg, which also provided raters for operational scoring. In accordance with similar studies undertaken by DPC, three types of ratings were employed for different sub-scales according to suitability (Bremerich-Vos & Scholten-Akoun, 2016). In the area of language quality, most ratings were done on a Likert scale (1–7), where 1 typically denoted “very high skills” and 7 “very low skills”. Raters either counted the number of instances (e.g., the number of structuring words) or the number of mistakes (e.g., number of wrongly used words), which directly yielded the skill level that was used in the statistical analysis (e.g., three structuring words = level 3). In the areas of structure and content, where assessment was focused more on the appropriateness of students’ writing, either binary ratings (0/1 = appropriate/inappropriate), or three-point ratings (3 = fully appropriate, 2 = partly appropriate, 1 = inappropriate) were used. These sub-scales and rating procedures are shown in Appendix 1 (Tables A1-A3).

After raters had assessed all sub-scales in the areas of language quality, structure and content, they were provided with an aggregated sum score and were asked for an additional, holistic assessment of each aspect. They were allowed to deviate from their sum score suggested by their individual scores but were asked not to do so without sufficient reason. In these additional scores, for example, raters could indicate that writers had attempted to include sophisticated vocabulary but had not been properly rewarded for taking that risk. Results showed that raters rarely deviated from their initial scores in the areas of language quality (3.1 %) and structure (2.1 %). Deviations were more frequent for content.

(17.3 %), maybe because larger portions of text (containing complex and manifold information) had to be evaluated in this area. In those cases where raters’ holistic impression differed from the original sum score, the additional score was included in further calculations of learners’ writing skills. Based on these ratings, we employed a three-dimensional many facets IRT rater modeling approach to receive a single score for each aspect of writing quality and normalized these scores the metric used in the (Programme for International Student Assessment PISA, 2000; see below, Sect. 3.6.1).

3.3.1. Language quality

The following sub-scales were used to assess language quality: lexical quality (correctness and variability of vocabulary; correctness of register; number and quality of structuring words), grammatical quality (correctness of grammar), and language mechanics (spelling, typos, punctuation). Typically, raters counted how often a certain event occurred in a text to produce an item score. For structuring words, for example, they counted genre-specific elements such as however, to conclude, etc. For correctness of vocabulary, they counted all words which were either wrongly used in context, missing, or superfluous.

3.3.2. Content

The following sub-scales were used to assess content: introducing the argument (topic becomes clear, hook to catch the reader’s attention, author’s opinion is apparent), presenting the argument (relevance of arguments for topic; arguments for both sides of the question are mentioned), and concluding the argument (author repeats opinion clearly). From a pedagogical point of view, these are generic aspects of content which are relevant in any argumentative text, irrespective of topic. This aspect thus expressed whether the individual parts of the essay contained the information they were supposed to contain, and whether learners had constructed a convincing argument to explain their point of view. For a high rating, learners also had to mention arguments for both sides. Raters

were not, however, asked to assess the factual truth of the arguments. Data for this study were collected in the context of timed writing where learners did not have the opportunity to research the topic or perform a detailed topical analysis. Different kinds of arguments were acceptable if the writer's position was clearly laid out in the beginning, supported by evidence in the main section and summarized succinctly in the end.

3.3.3. Structure

The following sub-scales were used to assess structure: introduction (present and clearly marked), conclusion (present and clearly marked), and use of paragraphs (dividing the text into meaningful units to guide the reader). The operationalization of structure was thus based on two factors: first, whether the text had paragraphs and whether they were used consistently to divide the arguments into meaningful units, thus making it easier for the reader to understand the writer's opinion. Second, whether the text had a clearly noticeable introduction and conclusion which was either marked linguistically (for example, by starting the first body paragraph with "the most important argument is..." or by announcing the conclusion with finally or to conclude). Alternatively, these parts had to be clearly marked by a paragraph or line break.

From the operationalization of structure and content in our study, it is apparent that these aspects are linked to some degree: only an existing introduction can be assessed in terms of content. A missing introduction thus lowers score both for structure and content. We expected these aspects to be correlated significantly while still assuming them to be conceptually sufficiently different to warrant separate interpretation. The conceptual overlap between content and structure is rooted in the multidimensional nature of argumentative essays, which also implies that analytic rating criteria overlap to some degree. However, this method of analysis is suitable for tracking EFL writing development, which is multidimensional rather than sequential, where growth takes place on many inter-related fronts at once, and which is continuous rather than lockstep (Sadler, 1989).

3.4. Rating procedures

The rating process was planned, executed, and evaluated by the author team in cooperation with experts from the IEA/DPC institute (see above) under the leadership of the main author. Six raters were chosen from a pool of raters from DPC who had participated in earlier, similar ratings of texts in English, had a good command of the English language and were familiar with the agency's procedures of assessment. We thus undertook the type of rigorous rater training which can mitigate differences in rater severity and consistency (Cushing, 2019).

In preparation for the ratings, raters were familiarized with the assessment system in a series of training sessions. In this process, benchmark texts for different levels of proficiency were identified and their features analyzed to create a common understanding of quality. Between training sessions, raters were asked to use the analytic criteria to assess a booklet of ten texts from a training sample. In the following training session, raters went through their ratings one by one. Consistency of assessments was checked, and raters were asked to explain their rationale if discrepancies appeared between ratings. In this process, some of the descriptions of sub-scales were adapted and categories deleted because no sufficient consistency between raters could be reached.

3.5. Interrater reliability

Each text was rated independently by two raters. After a first round of rater training, the interrater reliability was found to be satisfactory in general but not consistently above the threshold of weighted Kappa $> .6$ (.55 – .73). We reviewed all rater scores and found consistently divergent scores from one rater, who was excluded from further analyses. Operational ratings for the full sample were then performed in rater pairs from the pool of five people (see Appendix 2). This improved interrater reliability by $\Delta_{W-Kappa} = .07$ on average and lifted the overall reliabilities for all three scales to an acceptable level. The weighted Kappa was .74 for language quality, .70 for structure and .61 for content. Further, the reliabilities for all three aspects of writing quality were sufficient across both prompts. A complete confusion matrix for all operational raters and rater pairs across both prompts is shown in Appendix 3.

3.6. Statistical analyses

3.6.1. Modeling rater data

To receive a single score for each aspect of writing quality and each text, we employed a three-dimensional many facets IRT rater modeling approach (Robitzsch & Steinfeld, 2018; Wu, 2017). Using this approach allowed controlling for stable between-rater differences in severity / leniency, centrality / extremity, and rater discrimination, often referred to as rater accuracy or consistency (e.g., Uto & Ueno, 2020; Wu, 2017). We also accounted for differences in these rater effects across different aspects of writing quality (language quality vs. structure vs. content). To set up the model, the R-package TAM (Robitzsch & Steinfeld, 2018) was used (see Appendix 4 for details). Expected A Posteriori (EAP) scores were calculated and used as fair scores (i.e., adjusting for systematic rater effects) in further analyses (Eckes, 2015). EAP reliabilities for each scale were found to be good (language quality = .83; structure = .76; content = .78). Distribution of ratings on all scales is shown in Appendix 5.

To compare results between educational systems, we scaled the EAP factor scores for each analytic dimension to the PISA metric ($M = 500$, $SD = 100$). We thus aligned our analysis with prior studies of the same corpus (Keller et al., 2020) and used the preferred metric for comparing educational systems in Europe.

3.6.2. Missing data

Our strategy of sampling texts randomly from the original dataset for extended analytic analysis ($N = 2314$) implied that for some students only one of the essays (either from T1 or T2) was selected for the analytic assessment, while for some students both essays were selected. After the sampling procedure, the rate of missing data for the analytic ratings was 36.7 % across measurement points. Ratings of both measurement time points were available for 486 students in our sample. To account for missing data¹ and minimize missing data bias, we employed multiple imputation (MI), a state-of-the-art missing data treatment (Enders, 2010) using the R-packages *mice* (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) and *miceadds* (Robitzsch & Grund, 2021). Considering the nested structure of our data (students nested in schools), we applied a hierarchical MI scheme to produce 100 complete data sets for further analyses. MI involves predicting a plausible range of values for each missing data point based on the observed data. From this range of plausible values, the imputed values are repeatedly drawn for each of the 100 datasets. Sampling different plausible values represented in different datasets reflects the uncertainty about what the true value should be for each missing data point (Enders, 2010). Each analysis was repeated with each imputed dataset and parameter estimates were pooled afterwards.

3.6.3. Regression models and pooling

The research questions formulated in this study were addressed in two regression models. To account for the nested data structure, we applied a multilevel modeling approach with the R-package *lme4* (Bates, Mächler, Bolker & Walker, 2015). Since we had previously imputed 100 data sets, we used the common procedure of running each model on each data set separately before pooling the results (Enders, 2010). For this purpose, we used the routines implemented in the R-package *mitml* (Grund et al., 2016).

To address research RQ 1, we first ran a series of multilevel regression models with the dichotomous predictor *time* while controlling for the covariates *prompt* and *country*. To address RQ 2, which focused on differences between the two countries, we extended the interaction term between the factors *time* and *country* to examine differential gains among analytic criteria. For all the predictors and covariates, we used (weighted) effect coding (Hardy, 1993). In this approach, the main effects in the regression models can be interpreted as the average effect across the categories of the other covariates. The beta weights of the predictor and the covariates represent the difference between the group average and the category-specific averages. To obtain the actual group differences, beta coefficients must therefore be multiplied by two.

In total, we estimated four different effects (main effects for *time*, *country*, and *prompt*, and the moderation effect of *time* and *country*) for each of the three different analytic outcomes. We employed Bonferroni correction to address the multiple testing problem. Using the typical alpha-level $p < .05$ as baseline, the adjusted alpha level was $\alpha = \frac{.05}{4 \times 3} = .004$.

4. Results

4.1. Correlations between aspects of text quality

Table 2 presents the correlation coefficients between the three different scales. All correlations are significantly different from zero ($p < .001$). At both time points, the correlations were smallest between language quality and structure (.28 –.35), larger for language quality and content (.60 –.63), and largest for structure and content (.81 –.87). The intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) representing the proportion of the total variance of each outcome that was between classes (Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002) were .05 for language quality, .12 for structure and .07 for content. The variance between clusters turned out to be statistically significant (language quality: $F = 118.7$, $p < .001$; structure: $F = 337.5$, $p < .001$; content: $F = 164.2$, $p < .001$), indicating considerable performance differences between classes. These considerable level-2 differences between classes necessitated the application of multilevel regression models (Bates et al., 2015).

Table 2
Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations of Writing Skills Within and Across Time Points.

	Mean (SD)	Lang. Qual. T1	Structure T1	Content T1	Lang. Qual. T2	Structure T2
Lang. Qual. T1	493.3 (88.8)	-	-	-	-	-
Structure T1	479.1 (88.0)	.28	-	-	-	-
Content T1	488.8 (85.8)	.60	.81	-	-	-
Lang. Qual. T2	510.3 (92.9)	.64	.15	.35	-	-
Structure T2	523.8 (80.8)	.15	.24	.23	.35	-
Content T2	513.9 (91.7)	.32	.25	.30	.63	.87

Note. Correlation coefficients shaded in grey concern the same point of measurement (T1 / T2). All correlations were statistically significant at $p < .001$

¹ Note that most of the missing values were *missing completely at random* (MCAR) due to the random sampling of essays during the rating procedure (see, Enders, 2010). However, there is also a missing student essay quote of 15 % across measurement occasions in the MEWS corpus. These missing might not meet the MCAR assumption.

Table 3

Regression models. Standardized outcomes transformed to a metric with M = 500 and SD = 100.

Predictor	Language quality				Structure				Content			
	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p
Model 1												
Time	9.32	1.98	4.71	< .001	25.59	1.80	14.18	< .001	14.02	1.91	7.32	< .001
Country (Reference: Germany)	5.37	3.57	1.50	.133	22.15	3.90	5.67	< .001	9.80	3.77	2.60	.009
Prompt (Reference: AD)	-2.92	1.90	-1.54	.124	-2.17	1.77	-1.23	.219	-1.89	1.88	-1.01	.315
Model 2												
Time	9.32	1.98	4.71	< .001	25.59	1.78	14.41	< .001	14.02	1.91	7.33	< .001
Country (Reference: Germany)	5.37	3.57	1.50	.133	22.15	3.91	5.66	< .001	9.80	3.77	2.60	.009
Prompt (Reference: AD)	-2.92	1.90	-1.54	.124	-2.17	1.74	-1.25	.212	-1.89	1.88	-1.01	.315
Time*Country	0.23	1.96	0.12	.908	-18.94	2.04	-9.30	< .001	-3.16	2.08	-1.52	.129

Note. Significant effects listed in bold type.

Student-level R² of Models 1 (see, Raudenbush & Bryk, 2002): R²_{Lang.qual.} = .01 / R²_{Structure} = .07 / R²_{Content} = .02.

Student-level R² of Models 2: R²_{Lang.qual.} = .01 / R²_{Structure} = .11 / R²_{Content} = .02.

Bonferroni corrected alpha level: p < .004.

4.2. Development of learners' argumentative writing skills (RQ 1)

To answer RQ1, which concerned the development of learners' writing skills over the course of one school year, we ran three multilevel regression analyses, each including one of the text qualities as dependent variable (Table 3, Model 1). The text qualities were regressed on the predictor *time* as a dummy variable. We used effect coding, setting the first measurement time point (beginning of Year 11) to -1 and the second measurement time point to 1. In addition, we controlled for the factors *prompt* and *country* that were also effect coded. Results implied a significant improvement in all three aspects of writing quality (language quality: $b = 9.3, p < .001, R^2 = .01$; structure: $b = 25.6, p < .001, R^2 = .06$; content: $b = 14.0, p < .001, R^2 = .02$). Because the text qualities had been scaled onto a standardized metric with an overall mean of 500 and an overall standard deviation of 100, the regression coefficients can be interpreted as standardized effects. As is required in weighted effect coding, regression coefficients were multiplied by two to express actual group differences. Accordingly, on average, students improved around half of a standard deviation (i.e., about 45 points on the PISA metric) in structure, a quarter of a standard deviation (i.e., about 25 points on the PISA metric) in content, and less than one fifth of a standard deviation (i.e., about 17 points on the PISA metric) in language quality. The same patterns are reflected by the coefficients of determination (R²). According to Cohen's conventions, the coefficients of determination imply small effects for content (R² = .01) and language quality (R² = .02) and a medium effect for structure (R² = .06).

Apart from these main effects of the predictor time, only one further covariate effect was significant in this first series of regression

Fig. 1. Interaction Effect of Time*Country for Structure.

models (applying the Bonferroni corrected level of significance; Table 3, Model 1). It concerned the aspect of structure, where considerable performance differences became apparent between Swiss and German students. Across prompts and time points, the Swiss students scored almost half a standard deviation higher (about 45 points on the PISA scale) than the German students ($b = 22.2$, $p < .001$). To get a clearer picture of differences between countries, we also ran a second series of regression models (see also Fig. 1, below).

4.3. Country effects (RQ 2)

To analyze the influence of different (national) educational systems as a contextual factor on the writing performance gains, we included the interaction term between time and country as a further predictor in a second series of regression models (Table 3, Model 2). These interactions allowed us to investigate whether the learning gains between the two time points were associated with the educational system in which students were placed.

The results show a significant interaction and thus differential improvements in the two educational systems for the aspect of structure, but not for language quality and content. The significant interaction effect for structure is illustrated in Fig. 1.

As Fig. 1 shows, there are what appear to be considerable differences between Swiss and German students regarding their ability to structure argumentative essays at the beginning of Year 11. While Swiss learners initially did significantly better, German learners caught up over the course of one school year.

No such differential developments were observed for content and language quality, where development rates are consistent for the two countries: the quality of both aspects improved similarly in both countries, with Swiss students outperforming German ones at both time points (see Table 3, Model 2).

4.4. Further analyses: prompt effects

Although our study had no explicit focus on prompt effects, we tested for possible interactions between topic and writing skill by including the factor of prompt in both regression models (see above, Table 3). This was done mainly to check whether the sequence in which learners worked on the two prompts influenced the outcomes of our study. Results showed interaction effects between time and prompt for content ($b = -18.94$, $p < .001$) and language quality ($b = -13.49$, $p = .001$). Both interaction terms indicate that the time point at which participants worked on the prompts influenced the outcomes: at T1, the AD prompt seems to have been slightly more difficult for learners than the TE prompt (see Appendix 6 for a more detailed discussion of this effect).

5. Discussion

5.1. Analytic assessment of upper-secondary argumentative writing

This study investigated the development of learners' EFL argumentative writing skills in upper secondary education in Germany and Switzerland through analytic scoring. It focused on three broad aspects of EFL writing, integrating language quality, content and structure in its analytic framework. Its reach is thus broader than studies which have focused on linguistic aspects (e.g., Crossley, 2020) yet more detailed than studies based on holistic assessments (e.g., Keller et al., 2020). Results showed that all aspects of ESL writing skills were related to each other, revealing low correlations between language quality and structure (.28/.35), higher ones between language quality and content (.60 /.63) and the highest between structure and content (.81/.87). Despite these substantial intercorrelations, we would argue that the constructs are conceptually different enough to contribute to a better understanding of the internal structure of learner texts (Bae & Bachman, 2010). Further, it is helpful to distinguish between these aspects when giving feedback in the classroom, providing learners with instructional support that aligns with concrete strengths or weaknesses in their texts.

The aspect of structure, which has not been extensively studied in the literature so far, showed low correlations with language quality at both time points. It might represent a rather general argumentative writing strategy which students also encounter in their school language (German), and which can be transferred to some degree between languages (Berman, 1994; Bremerich-Vos & Scholten-Akoun, 2016). The features of language quality, by contrast, tap into general aspects of L2 proficiency where progress is slow and incremental (e.g., complex grammatical constructions or genre- and topic specific idiomatic language; Ellis, 2008). This would explain why we see larger improvement for structure than we do for language quality over one school year.

Correlations were larger for language quality and content at both time points, suggesting a link between the ability to build a convincing argument (with adequate support) and the ability to express that argument in appropriate words and grammatical structures. As Bae et al. (2016) point out, "writers do not arrange words at random but in accordance with grammatical and discourse rules to make a text comprehensible. So, clearly, words, grammar, and discourse conventions are used in the service of content" (p. 303). From a classroom perspective, it is vital to recognize the close connection of language quality and content. Especially at upper-secondary level, command of complex linguistic skills is required of learners to present claims, make arguments and add convincing support (Crossley, 2020; Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008). Teaching and practicing such skills explicitly are likely to benefit the content dimension of essays as well.

Correlations were largest between structure and content at both time points, which was due in part to our operationalization (see Sect. 3.3.3). The close link between these aspects also suggests a conceptual connection, as the ability of building a convincing argument overlaps with the ability of presenting this argument in an introduction, a main part, and a conclusion. This connection

might be used as a lever for teaching in the EFL classroom. For example, learners could study model texts for their content (or argumentation) while simultaneously analyzing how that content is represented in the typical paragraph structure of the genre (Hyland, 2008; Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008).

5.2. Longitudinal development

In terms of development over time, the learning gains over one school year are consistent with those found in other studies both in Germany (Brunner et al., 2023) and internationally (Bloom et al., 2008; see Sect. 2.9, above). Our study found improvements for all aspects of writing over one year, with the largest effect for structure (half of a standard deviation; $R^2 = .06$) and smaller effects for content (quarter of a standard deviation; $R^2 = .01$) and language quality (one fifth of a standard deviation; $R^2 = .02$).

The relatively small gains in language quality and content are in range with growth effects at upper-secondary level in different subjects (Bloom et al., 2008). Further, it has been shown that learning rates in English slow down even further at higher levels of schooling (deceleration effect; Leucht, Retelsdorf, Pant, Möller & Köller, 2015). Our results suggest that there is significant potential for improvement where linguistic aspects of text quality are concerned as gaining mastery of genre-specific argumentative language requires extended classroom input and practice (Keller, 2013). There is evidence that from Year 8 onwards, English teachers in Germany use large parts of their lessons to explain and practice formal language skills with their students (Helmke, Helmke, Schrader, Wagner, Nold & Schröder, 2008). Further research is needed to understand how to tailor that support specifically to learners in upper-secondary education. In the context of argumentative EFL writing, this could be done in intervention studies where learners are taught genre-specific language skills. This might include modals and modal alternatives (e.g., “ought to – it is essential that”), argumentative language suitable for developing and structuring an argument (e.g., “however”, “therefore”), or language to contrast arguments and counterarguments (e.g., “some people believe ... However, it must also be recognized that”; “While it is true that ... it can also be argued that”; Zemach & Stafford-Yilmaz, 2008). The hypothesis would be that instruction in those genre-specific aspects of language quality would speed up development where, in this study, it was shown to be the slowest.

In terms of structure, our results suggest that students seem to be quite able to divide a text into an introduction, a main part, and a conclusion (at least at T2). This is remarkable as the study by Siekmann (2022) had shown that structure posed a major challenge for EFL learners at lower secondary level. Our study showed steep gains for this aspect above all in the German sample, where aspects related to structure are explicitly mentioned in assessment criteria for the final exams. However, the fact that our analysis of structure was skewed towards high ratings (see Appendix 5) might also indicate that our operationalization was too narrow for this age group. Future studies should look not only at the existence of elements such as introduction, main part, and conclusion, but also analyze their internal quality.

5.3. Differences between countries

Results show that Swiss learners outperformed German learners in all aspects of text quality at both time-points, which is consistent with the holistic ratings of the same corpus (Keller et al., 2020). We believe that reason for Swiss learners' generally higher writing skills lies in the fact that access to upper-secondary education is more restricted in Switzerland, with only the highest-performing learners proceeding to that school type. The steep gains which German learners showed over one school year (particularly in the aspect of structure, see Fig. 1) can be seen as testimony to the quality of instruction in German Gymnasiums. Aspects of structure and argumentation play a central role in German national educational standards and test tasks (IQB, 2021), indicating a backwash effect. However, the consistently high scores for structure in both countries also suggest a ceiling effect which should be examined in future studies.

5.4. Limitations and further research

In this study, we frequently refer to learners' writing skills but should keep in mind that we only measured performance in two writing tasks. To have a more reliable measure of writings skills, one would have to assess learners' performance in a larger variety of situations and contexts. We should also keep in mind that only one year was examined and it is unclear whether the same trajectory of learning gains holds for each year of secondary education. Furthermore, issues with reliability of some of our individual items underlying the three aspects of writing quality prevented us from analyzing texts at a more fine-grained level. Reliability improved when these items were summarized into broader aspects of writing, but detailed information about internal structure (e.g., grammar and vocabulary within language quality) was lost along the way.

Further, it is unclear how well students' skills shown in timed writing can be extrapolated to authentic, disciplinary writing tasks in other contexts. Previous studies have examined the correlation between learners' scores on TOEFL iBT independent prompts and authentic writing tasks in higher education, finding only weak to moderate correlations between the two (Cho & Bridgeman, 2012; Ginther & Yan, 2017). While providing a solid indication of learners' argumentative writing skills, timed impromptu essay writing is limited in terms of its generalizability to other academic genres (Staples et al., 2018). It is equally unclear to what extent the results of this study can be generalized beyond the geo-educational context of Switzerland and Germany. One could argue that these countries, with their shared emphasis on English as a gateway to academic success, are representative of a range of countries in (or associated with) the European union. As English as a second or foreign language is taught all over the world, results might be relevant for EFL writing beyond the European context, for example for English L2 learners in America (Francis et al., 2002). Based on the available studies, however, it stands to reason that the development of writing skills might be different for learners in other cultures with

differing school languages (e.g., Chinese, see [Ling et al., 2014](#)). [Green \(2005\)](#), for example, compared the writing scores of a large sample of writers in the IELTS writing tests over a period of several years and found considerable individual variation in the rate of writing score gains according to test-taker age and region of origin (e.g., East Asia vs. Europe). It would be useful to have more studies with a similarly broad operationalization of writing skills (including *linguistic*, *structural* and content-related features) to understand how EFL writing development differs across geographical spaces and educational systems.

Additionally, it would be valuable to study in more detail how individual aspects of writing quality develop in the context of classroom teaching, either in observation studies or interventions. The results of this study are useful to gauge which aspects of EFL argumentative writing such future studies should focus on. Yet while textual analyses provide accurate, detailed information about the quality of learners' texts, they also raise important questions about the kind of instruction that produced these gains in understanding and skill, and the perspectives of teachers and students about specific challenges and their strategies they employed. For example, our data suggests that language quality should be a focus of attention, i.e., mastering the complex lexical and grammatical structures that constitute English argumentative language and create the difference between a loosely structured opinion piece and a persuasive, compelling English argumentative essay. The larger question remains of how to integrate that formal focus with a classroom approach that encourages learners to find meaning in writing tasks, to revise their texts substantially in response to (peer) feedback, and to progress substantially in ESL writing by drawing on a wide range of linguistic and personal resources. Such questions go largely unanswered in this study but should take a prominent place in future ones.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Johanna Fleckenstein: Conceptualization. **Ruth Trueb:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Jennifer Meyer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Jens Möller:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thorben Jansen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Julian Lohmann:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stefan Daniel Keller:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix 1. Analytic assessment scheme (sub-scales) employed in this study

Table A1
Assessment Criteria, Subscales and Type of Assessment for Language Quality.

Aspect	Variable	Assessment type
Lexical quality	Correctness of vocabulary	1
	Variability of vocabulary	2
	Register (degree of formality, overly informal expressions)	2
	Number of structuring words	1
	Quality of structuring words	2
	Correctness of grammar	1
	Spelling / Orthography	1
Grammatical quality and language mechanics	Typos	2
	Punctuation	1

Note. 1 = Likert scale (1-7 based on number of mistakes or instances of a phenomenon); 2 = binary coding (*appropriate / inappropriate*)

Table A2
Assessment Criteria and Sub-scales for Content.

Aspect	Variable	Assessment type
Introduction	Topic of essay becomes clear	2
	Hook (author attempts to catch the reader's attention)	2
	Author's own opinion is made clear	2
Main body of essay	Arguments for both sides of the question are mentioned	3
Conclusion	Author repeats opinion clearly	2
	Relevance of arguments for prompt	3
Argumentation	Importance of arguments is marked	2

Note. 2 = binary coding (appropriate / inappropriate), 3 = Likert scale (fully appropriate, party appropriate, inappropriate)

Table A3
Assessment Criteria and Sub-Scales for Structure.

Aspect	Variable	Assessment type
Paragraphs	Use of paragraphs	3
	Existence of an introduction	2
Introduction	Explicit marking of the introduction	2
	Existence of a conclusion	2
Conclusion	Explicit marking of the conclusion	2

Note. 2 = binary coding (appropriate / inappropriate), 3 = Likert scale (fully appropriate, party appropriate, inappropriate)

Appendix 2. Rating design and rater pairs used in this study

Table A4
Rater Pairs for All Texts.

	01/02	01/03	01/04	01/05	01/06	02/03	02/04	02/05	02/06	03/04	03/05	03/06	04/05	04/06	05/06
N (TE)	71	60	43	64	75	99	57	98	81	58	82	97	71	52	112
N (AD)	82	73	58	73	74	100	51	112	93	54	111	99	40	46	103
N (total)	153	133	101	137	149	199	108	210	174	112	193	196	111	98	215

Appendix 3. Interrater reliability

Highlighted area in content concerns rater 2, whose reliability was consistently lower than that of the other raters and who was therefore excluded from further analysis.

Table A5
Confusion Matrices for Interrater Reliability (Cohen's Kappa).

A5.1 Language Quality						
	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 3	Rater 4	Rater 5	Rater 6
Rater 1	-	0.609	0.792	0.734	0.763	0.734
Rater 2	0.609	-	0.686	0.714	0.653	0.664
Rater 3	0.792	0.686	-	0.69	0.762	0.752
Rater 4	0.734	0.714	0.69	-	0.661	0.592
Rater 5	0.763	0.653	0.762	0.661	-	0.736
Rater 6	0.734	0.664	0.752	0.592	0.736	-
A5.2 Structure						
	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 3	Rater 4	Rater 5	Rater 6
Rater 1	-	0.786	0.806	0.719	0.706	0.738
Rater 2	0.786	-	0.801	0.64	0.655	0.752
Rater 3	0.806	0.801	-	0.695	0.737	0.824
Rater 4	0.719	0.64	0.695	-	0.585	0.733
Rater 5	0.706	0.655	0.737	0.585	-	0.66

(continued on next page)

Table A5 (continued)

A5.2 Structure						
	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 3	Rater 4	Rater 5	Rater 6
Rater 6	0.738	0.752	0.824	0.733	0.66	-
A5.3 Content						
	Rater 1	Rater 2	Rater 3	Rater 4	Rater 5	Rater 6
Rater 1	-	0.524	0.659	0.548	0.622	0.698
Rater 2	0.524	-	0.554	0.432	0.401	0.488
Rater 3	0.659	0.554	-	0.573	0.675	0.649
Rater 4	0.548	0.432	0.573	-	0.542	0.55
Rater 5	0.622	0.401	0.675	0.542	-	0.597
Rater 6	0.698	0.488	0.649	0.55	0.597	-

As Table A5.3 shows, coefficients are consistently lower for rater 2, who was subsequently excluded from the analysis (shaded numbers).

Table A6

Interrater Reliabilities for the Three Aspects of Writing quality, Differentiated by Writing Prompt.

	Interrater correlation Mean	Interrater correlation Median	Weighted Cohen's Kappa Mean	Weighted Cohen's Kappa Median
Language quality	0.75	0.77	0.72	0.74
Prompt AD	0.73	0.73	0.71	0.71
Prompt TE	0.75	0.76	0.72	0.73
Structure	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.73
Prompt AD	0.68	0.70	0.68	0.70
Prompt TE	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.76
Content	0.64	0.64	0.61	0.61
Prompt AD	0.68	0.70	0.66	0.67
Prompt TE	0.56	0.57	0.52	0.52

Appendix 4. Model fits and comparisons between models

To account for stable between-rater differences and to obtain text-quality scores adjusted for these stable “rater-effects”, we chose an IRT-based many-facets rater modeling approach. In doing so, we set up a series of models and performed stepwise model extensions (Robitzsch & Steinfeld, 2018). We started with a restrictive model, only considering independent effects for each item (language quality vs. structure vs. content), rater, and item-categories (category-steps ranging from 0 to 6). Next, we incorporated step-by-step interaction terms between these three factors until we reached the full many-facets Rasch model (MFRM) (item*step*rater) (models 1.1–1.5). We found that the most complex model (model 1.5) fitted the data best (see Table A7). It encompassed rater-specific leniency / severity and extremity / centrality differing across items.

In a final step, we also tested for differences in rater-discrimination, often referred to as rater consistency or rater accuracy (Model 2.1–2.2). Again, we considered interactions with items (Model 2.2). Fit statistics implied considerable between-rater differences in rater-discrimination varying across items. Thus, we used Model 2.2, the most complex model, to calculate the fair scores for further analyses. In doing so, we accounted for between-rater differences in leniency / severity, extremity / centrality and discrimination (Uto & Ueno, 2020).

Table A7

Fits and Model Comparisons.

	Effects	Npars	Deviance	AIC	BIC	Chi ²	df	p (LRT)
Model 1.0	Item + rater	13	41899.5	41925.5	42000.2	-	-	-
Model 1.1	Item + step + rater	18	32648.7	32684.7	32788.1	9250.8	5	< .001
Model 1.2	Item*step + rater	28	31496.4	31552.4	31713.3	1152.3	10	< .001
Model 1.3	Item*step + item*rater	36	31195.6	31267.6	31474.5	300.7	8	< .001
Model 1.4	Item*step + item*rater + step*rater	56	30964.7	31076.7	31398.6	230.9	20	< .001
Model 1.5	Item*step*rater	96	30653.4	30845.4	31397.1	311.3	40	< .001
Model 2.1	Model 1.5 + rater discrimination	98	31690.2	31886.2	32449.4	-1036.9	2	1
Model 2.2	Model 1.5 + rater*item discrimination	108	30600.1	30816.1	31436.8	1090.1	10	< .001

Appendix 5

Fig. A1. Distribution of Ratings for the Three aspects of text quality. Note. Likert scale (0 = very low quality; 6 = very high quality).

Appendix 6

Table A8

Exploring Interaction Effects Among Factors Prompt, Time, and Country.

Predictor	Language quality				Structure				Content			
	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p
Time	9.29	1.97	4.73	< .001	51.18	3.61	14.18	< .001	25.54	1.78	14.37	< .001
Country	5.30	3.56	1.49	0.136	-4.45	3.55	-1.25	0.210	22.17	3.92	5.65	< .001
Prompt (Reference: AD)	-2.92	1.88	-1.55	0.121	25.59	1.78	14.41	< .001	-2.17	1.74	-1.25	0.212

(continued on next page)

Table A8 (continued)

Predictor	Language quality				Structure				Content			
	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p	Est.	SE	t	p
Time*Country	-0.12	1.95	-0.06	0.951	22.15	3.91	5.66	< .001	-1.38	1.88	-0.73	0.463
Time*Prompt	-13.49	1.90	-7.11	< .001	-2.17	1.74	-1.25	0.212	-18.94	2.04	-9.28	< .001
Time*Country*Prompt	3.73	1.96	1.90	0.058	-18.94	2.04	-9.30	< .001	-1.37	1.79	-0.76	0.445

Prompt effects were inserted as predictors of writing skills in our regression models. The prompt dummy was effect coded with reference AD. The analysis presented in Table A9 revealed significant interaction effects between time and prompt for content ($b = -18.94, p < .001$) and language quality ($b = -13.49, p = .001$). Both interaction terms indicate that the time at which learners worked on those prompts (T1 or T2) is correlated significantly with the scores they achieved for those prompts. These interaction effects are illustrated in Figure A2.

Fig. A2. Differences Between the Prompts Relating to Language quality (A) and Content (B) Regarding the Sequence in which Learners Worked on Them.

As Figure A2 shows, the growth which observe in the aspects of language quality and content was influenced in part by the sequence in which students worked on the two prompts. Students who first worked on AD had slightly lower scores than students who worked on TE at T1. Conversely, students who worked on AD second had slightly higher scores than those who worked on TE at T2. One reason might be that AD was a relatively abstract and distal topic for the learners in our sample and was therefore more difficult to do at T1 (see also Atak & Saricaoglu, 2021). We noticed in the rating process that many learners did not properly understand that this prompt required them to discuss the specific dangers of advertising directed at very young children. Instead, they often wrote about the dangers of excessive TV watching in general. For students who worked on AD at T2, it seems to have been easier to overcome those challenges, leading to slightly better results both in content and in language quality (which also included aspects of topic-specific vocabulary). This would also explain why structure, which was the most general aspect of text quality in our operationalization, was not affected by this effect.

References

- Akukwe, B., Grotjahn, R., & Schipolowski, S. (2017). *Schreibkompetenzen in der Fremdsprache: Aufgabengestaltung, kriterienorientierte Bewertung und Feedback [Writing competences in foreign languages: Tasks, assessment, feedback]*. Narr.
- Andrade, H. G. (2005). Teaching with rubrics: The good, the bad, and the ugly. *College Teaching*, 53(1), 27–31. <https://doi.org/10.3200/CTCH.53.1.27-31>
- Atak, N., & Saricaoglu, A. (2021). Syntactic complexity in L2 learners' argumentative writing: Developmental stages and the within-genre topic effect. *Assessing Writing*, 47, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2020.100506>
- Bae, J., & Bachman, L. (2010). An investigation of four writing traits and two tasks across two languages. *Language Testing*, 27(2), 213–234. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532209349470>
- Bae, J., Bentler, P., & Lee, Y. (2016). On the role of content in writing assessment. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 13(4), 302–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2016.1246552>
- Barkaoui, K., & Hadidi, A. (2020). *Assessing change in English second language writing performance*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003092346>
- Barkaoui, K. (2010). Variability in ESL essay rating processes: The role of the rating scale and rater experience. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 7, 54–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434300903464418>
- Barkaoui, K. (2007). Rating scale impact on EFL essay marking: A mixed-method study. *Assessing Writing*, 12, 86–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2007.07.001>
- Bacha, N. (2001). Writing evaluation: What can analytic versus holistic essay scoring tell us? *System*, 29(3), 371–383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0346-251X\(01\)00025-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0346-251X(01)00025-2)

- Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015). Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 67(1), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>
- Berman, R. (1994). Learners' transfer of writing skills between languages. *TESL Canada Journal*, 12, 29–46.
- Bloom, H. S., Hill, C. J., Black, A. R., & Lipsey, M. W. (2008). Performance trajectories and performance gaps as achievement effect-size benchmarks for educational interventions. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 1(4), 289–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19345740802400072>
- Bhatia, V. K. (2004). *Worlds of written discourse: A genre-based view*. Continuum.
- Bremerich-Vos, A., & Scholten-Akoun, D. (2016). *Schriftsprachliche Kompetenzen von Lehramtsstudierenden in der Studiengangphase: Eine empirische Untersuchung [Writing competences of beginning students in teacher education: An empirical study]*. Schneider.
- Brunner, M., Stallassch, S. E., & Lüdtke, O. (2023). Empirical benchmarks to interpret intervention effects on student achievement in elementary and secondary school: Meta-analytic results from Germany. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19345747.2023.2175753>
- Cho, Y., & Bridgeman, B. (2012). Relationship of TOEFL iBT scores to academic performance: Some evidence from American universities. *Language Testing*, 29, 421–442.
- Choi, I., & Papageorgiou, S. (2014). *Monitoring students' progress in English language skills using the TOEFL ITP assessment series* (Research Memorandum No. RM-14–11). Educational Testing Service.
- Council of Europe. (2001). Common European framework of reference for languages. Cambridge.
- Crossley, S. A. (2020). Linguistic features in writing quality and development: An overview. *Journal of Writing Research*, 11(3), 415–443. <https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2020.11.03.01>
- Cumming, A. (2012). Writing development in second language acquisition. In C. A. Chapelle (Ed.), *The encyclopedia of applied linguistics* (1st ed., pp. 34–56). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405198431.wbeal1299>.
- Cushing, S. T. (2019). Assessment of writing. In C. A. Chapelle (Ed.), *The encyclopedia of applied linguistics* (1st ed., pp. 1–7). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405198431.wbeal0056.pub2>.
- Eckes, T. (2015). *Introduction to many-facet Rasch measurement: Analyzing and evaluating rater-mediated assessments* (Second ed.). Peter Lang.
- Ellis, R. (2008). Second language acquisition studies. Oxford.
- Educational Testing Service [ETS]. (2009). *The official guide to the TOEFL test*. McGraw-Hill.
- Ferretti, R. P., & Lewis, W. E. (2019). Best practices in teaching argumentative writing. In S. Graham, C. A. MacArthur, & J. Fitzgerald (Eds.), *Best practices in writing instruction* (3rd ed., pp. 135–161). Guilford Press.
- Fleckenstein, J., Keller, S., Krüger, M., Tannenbaum, R., & Köller, O. (2019). Linking TOEFL iBT® writing rubrics to CEFR levels: Cut scores and validity evidence from a standard setting study. *Assessing Writing*, 41, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2019.100420>
- Francis, W. S., Romo, L. F., & Gelman, R. (2002). Syntactic structure, grammatical accuracy, and content in second-language writing: An analysis of skill learning and on-line processing. In R. R. Heredia, & J. Altarriba (Eds.), *Advances in psychology* (Vol. 134, pp. 317–337). North-Holland. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4115\(02\)80017-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4115(02)80017-6).
- Ginther, A., & Yan, X. (2017). Interpreting the relationships between TOEFL iBT scores and GPA: Language proficiency, policy, and profiles. *Language Testing*, 35(2), 271–295. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532217704010>
- Green, A. (2005). EAP study recommendations and score gains on the IELTS academic writing test. *Assessing Writing*, 10, 44–60.
- Graham, S., Kihara, S. A., & MacKay, M. (2020). The effects of writing on learning in science, social studies, and mathematics: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(2), 179–226. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543201914744>
- Grotjahn, R., & Kleppin, K. (2017). Kriteriale Evaluation von Schreibkompetenzen [Criterion assessment of writing competences. In B. Akukwe, R. Grotjahn, & S. Schipolowski (Eds.), *Schreibkompetenzen in der Fremdsprache. Aufgabengestaltung, kriterienorientierte Bewertung und Feedback [Writing competences in foreign languages. Tasks, assessment, feedback]* (pp. 117–157). Narr.
- Grund, S., Robitzsch, A., & Lüdtke, O. (2016). Package 'mitml'. Retrieved from (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mitml/>).
- Hardy, M. A. (1993). *Regression with dummy variables*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Helmke, T., Helmke, A., Schrader, F., Wagner, W., Nold, G., & Schröder, K. (2008). Die Videostudie des Englischunterrichts [Video study of English teaching. In DESI-Konsortium (Ed.), Ed.), *Unterricht und Kompetenzerwerb in Deutsch und Englisch. [Teaching quality and competence gain in German and English]*. Beltz. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:3521>.
- Huot, B. (1990). Reliability, validity, and holistic scoring: What we know and what we need to know. *College Composition and Communication*, 41(2), 201–213.
- Hyland, K. (1990). A genre description of the argumentative essay. *REL C Journal*, 21(1), 66–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003368829002100105>
- Hyland, K. (2008). *Second language writing*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jacobs, H., Zinkgraf, S., Wormuth, D., Hearfield, V., & Hughey, J. (1981). Testing ESL Composition: A Practical Approach. Retrieved from (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/247716030_Testing_ESL_Composition_a_Practical_Approach#fullTextFileContent) (Accessed 23 November 2023).
- Keller, S., Fleckenstein, J., Krüger, M., Köller, O., & Rupp, A. (2020). English writing skills of students in upper secondary education: Results from an empirical study in Switzerland and Germany. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 48, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jslw.2019.100700>
- Keller, S. (2013). Integrative Schreibdidaktik Englisch für die Sekundarstufe. Theorie, Prozessgestaltung, Empirie [Integrated teaching of writing at secondary level. Theory, process design, research]. Narr.
- Kim, M. (2021). Considerations and challenges in longitudinal studies of lexical features in L2 writing. *Vocabulary Learning and Instruction*, 10(2), 82–90. <https://doi.org/10.7820/vli.v10.2.kramer>
- Köller, O., Knigge, M., & Tesch, B. (2010). Sprachliche Kompetenzen im Ländervergleich. [National comparison of language competences]. Waxmann.
- Kyle, K., Crossley, S., & Verspoor, M. (2021). Measuring longitudinal writing development using indices of syntactic complexity and sophistication. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 43(4), 781–812. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263120000546>
- Landrieu, Y., De Smedt, F., Van Keer, H., & De Wever, B. (2022). Assessing the quality of argumentative texts: Examining the general agreement between different rating procedures and exploring inferences of (dis)agreement cases. *Frontiers in Education*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.784261>
- Leucht, M., Retelsdorf, J., Pant, H. A., Möller, J., & Köller, O. (2015). Effekte der Gymnasialprofilzugehörigkeit auf Leistungsentwicklungen im Fach Englisch [Effects of Gymnasium profile on performance development in English]. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogische Psychologie*, 29(2), 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1010-0652/a000153>
- Ling, G., Powers, D.E., & Adler, R.M. (2014). *Do TOEFL iBT scores reflect improvement in English-language proficiency? Extending the TOEFL iBT validity argument* (Research Report No. RR-14–09). Educational Testing Service.
- Lu, X. (2011). A corpus-based evaluation of syntactic complexity measures as indices of college-level ESL writers' language development. *TESOL Quarterly*, 45(1), 36–62. <https://doi.org/10.5054/tq.2011.240859>
- Pohlmann-Rother, S., Schoreit, E., & Kürzinger, A. (2016). Schreibkompetenzen von Erstklässlern quantitativ-empirisch erfassen - Herausforderungen und Zugewinn eines analytisch-kriterialen Vorgehens gegenüber einer holistischen Bewertung. [Quantitative assessment of first graders' writing competences – challenges and advantages of analytical vs. holistic assessment. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 8(2), 107–135. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:12429>
- Polio, C. (2017). Second language writing development: A research agenda. *Language Teaching*, 50(2), 261–275. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000015>
- National Statistical Office of Switzerland [BFS]. (2016). Maturitätsquote. [Rate of Matura exams]. Retrieved from (<https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home>) (Accessed 9 June 2024).
- Programme for International Student Assessment [PISA]. (2000). PISA 2000. Basiskompetenzen von Schülerinnen und Schülern im internationalen Vergleich [Basic competences of students in international comparison]. Leske & Budrich.
- Raudenbush, S. W., & Bryk, A. S. (2002). *Hierarchical linear models: Applications and data analysis methods* (Vol. 1). Sage.
- Robitzsch, A., & Grund, S. (2021). *Miceadds: Some additional multiple imputation functions, especially for 'mice'*. R package version 3.11–6. Retrieved from (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=miceadds>) (last accessed on 9.6.2024).

- Robitzsch, A., & Steinfeld, J. (2018). Item response models for human ratings: Overview, estimation methods, and implementation. *R Psychological Test and Assessment Modeling*, 60(1), 101–139. (https://www.psychologie-aktuell.com/fileadmin/download/ptam/1-2018_20180323/6_PTAM_IRMHR_Main_2018-03-13_1416.pdf).
- Rupp, A., Casabianca, J., Krüger, M., Keller, S., & Köller, O. (2019). Automated essay scoring at scale: A case study in Switzerland and Germany (TOEFL Research Report No. RR-86). *Educational Testing Service*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ets2.12249>
- Sadler, R. (1989). Formative assessment and the design of instructional systems. *Instructional Science*, 18, 119–144. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00117714>
- Schipolowski, S., & Böhme, K. (2016). Assessment of writing ability in secondary education: Comparison of analytic and holistic scoring systems for use in large-scale assessments. *L1 Educational Studies in Language and Literature*, 16(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.17239/L1ESLL-2016.16.01.03>
- Schnoor, B., & Ursanova, I. (2022). Multilingual writing development: Relationships between writing proficiencies in German, heritage language, and English. *Reading and Writing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-022-10276-4>
- Schoonen, R. (2005). Generalizability of writing scores: An application of structural equation modeling. *Language Testing*, 22, 1–30.
- Siekmann, L., Parr, J., & Busse, V. (2022). Structure and coherence as challenges in composition: A study of assessing less proficient EFL writers' text quality. *Assessing Writing*, 54, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2022.100672>
- Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs of the Länder in the Federal Republic of Germany [KMK]. (2018). Schüler, Klassen, Lehrer und Absolventen der Schulen 2007–2016 [Students, classes, teachers and graduates of schools 2007–2016]. (<https://www.kmk.org/dokumentation-statistik/statistik/schulstatistik/schueler-klassen-lehrer-und-absolventen.html>) (last accessed on 9.6.2024).
- Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs of the Länder in the Federal Republic of Germany [KMK]. (2014). Bildungsstandards für die fortgeführte Fremdsprache (Englisch/Französisch) für die Allgemeine Hochschulreife [Educational standards for foreign languages (English / French) for upper secondary education]. Wolters.
- Staples, S., Biber, D., & Reppen, R. (2018). Using corpus-based register analysis to explore the authenticity of high-stakes language exams: A register comparison of TOEFL iBT and disciplinary writing tasks. *The Modern Language Journal*, 102(2), 310–332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12465>
- Swiss Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education [EDK] (Eds.). (1994). Rahmenlehrplan für die Maturitätsschulen [National curriculum for upper secondary schools]. EDK.
- Tardy, C. (2006). Researching first and second language genre learning: A comparative review and a look ahead. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 15(2), 79–101.
- Tardy, C., & Swales, J. (2014). Genre analysis. In K. P. Schneider, & A. Barron (Eds.), *Pragmatics of Discourse* (pp. 165–187). De Gruyter.
- Trüb, R. (2022). An Empirical Study of EFL Writing at Primary School. Narr.
- Uto, M., & Ueno, M. (2020). A generalized many-facet Rasch model and its Bayesian estimation using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *Behaviormetrika*, 47, 469–496. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41237-020-00115-7>
- van Buuren, S., & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, K. (2011). Mice: Multivariate imputation by chained equations. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 45(3), 1–67. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v045.i03>
- Verspoor, M. (2017). Complex dynamic systems theory and L2 pedagogy. In L. Ortega, & Z. Han (Eds.), *Complexity Theory and Language Development: In celebration of Diane Larsen-Freeman* (Vol. 48, pp. 143–162). John Benjamins.
- Wu, M. (2017). Some IRT-based analyses for interpreting rater effects. *Psychological Test and Assessment Modeling*, 59(4), 453–470.
- Zemach, D., & Stafford-Yilmaz, L. (2008). *Writers at work. The essay*. Cambridge University Press.